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Domestic Violence among Working Women in Context of Emotional Intelligence, Desire for Social Freedom and Marital Adjustment

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The present empirical study was conducted on 80 working and 80 non-working women of Patna town. The sample were selected using incidental-cum-purposive sampling technique. The main purpose of the study was to examine the effect of EI, working and non-working dimensions, desire for social freedom and marital adjustment on domestic violence. For the purpose, emotional intelligence, domestic violence, women's desire for social freedom and marital adjustment were measured using Mangal's EI Scale, Kumar's Domestic Violence Scale, Bhushan's Women's Desire for Social Freedom Scale and Marital Adjustment Questionnaires by Kumar and Rahtogi respectively. Besides these, a PDS was used to get the other necessary informations relating to the respondents. The scales were employed and data were obtained as per directions of manuals of the scales concerned. The data were analysed using t-test. The results confirmed all the formulated hypotheses. It was concluded that : (i) more emotionally intelligent women respondents are less prone to domestic violence than their counterparts, (ii) working women are more prone and exposed to domestic violence than non-working women, (iii) the women desirous for more social freedom are more likely to be the victim of domestic violence, and (iv) women with poor marital adjustment are more exposed to domestic violence than women having sound marital adjustment.

Introduction

The first component is domestic violence (DV) which refers to patterns of behaviour characterized by the misuse of power and controlled by one person over another who are or have been in an intimate relationship. It can occur in mixed gender relationship and same gender relationship and has profound consequences for the lives of children, individual, families and communities. It may be physical, sexual, emotional and/or psychological. The second component is emotional intelligence (EI) which refers to the encompassing abilities to perceive accurate, appraise and express emotion; The ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; The ability to understand emotions and emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotion to promote emotional and intellectual growth (Mayer and Solovency, 1997). Another component of the present study is women's desire for social freedom which refers to women's desire to be free from social taboos, convention, rituals and roles which provide them with lower states in society. In recent years, desire for social freedom among women has manifested itself in protest and revolt against the traditional and moral values which place them in interior roles and status as compare to their male counterparts. One component is marital adjustment which is a multidimensional indicator of the quality of marital relationship. It is the process of mutual adjustment between husband and wife in all aspects of their life. Controversy to it, marital maladjustment is the disharmony or disequilibrium between husband and wife which leads to problem in their married life.

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Several study have been concluded in India and abroad relating to investigate in to the effect of various personality factors, psychological factors, social factors, motivational factors on various firms of domestic violence among working and non-working women including tribal and non-tribal cultures (Agarwal, 2007; Ballabh 2006; Bharti 2006; Dwivedi 2007; Kumar 2005, 2007; Kumari & Kumar 2007; Rani 2006; Ranjan, 2007; Vijyalakshmi 2006). So, there is shortage of relevant studies relating to the variables under reference.

Objectives

The present study was conducted with the following objectives

- to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on domestic violence of the respondent.
- to examine the effect of working and non-working dimensions on domestic violence of the respondent.
- to examine the effect of women's desire for social freedom on domestic violence of the respondent.
- to examine the influence of marital adjustment on domestic violence of respondent.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for empirical verification

- (i) There would be significant effect of emotional intelligence on domestic violence of the respondent.
- (ii) There would be significant effect of working status of women on domestic violence of the respondent.
- (iii) Women's desire for social freedom would have significant influence on domestic violence of the respondents.
- (iv) Marital adjustment would have significant effect on domestic violence of the respondents.

Method of Study

Sample Used

The study was conducted on working (N=80) and non-working (N=80) woman selected from Patna. The working women were selected from among different organisations of Patna. The non-working were house wives. Other than the research conditions they were matched so far as practicable.

Research Tools Used

- A Personal Data Sheet was used to get the necessary informations about the respondents.
- Emotional Intelligence Scale by Mangal's and Mangal's was used to measure emotional intelligence to the respondents.
- Women's Social Freedom Scale by Bhushan was used to measure the desire for social freedom of the respondents.
- Marital Adjustment Questionnaire by Kumar and Rohatogi was used to assess marital adjustment amongst women.
- Domestic Violence Scale by Kumar D (self developed) was used to measure domestic violence of the respondents.

Procedure of Data Collection

The researcher personally approaches to the respondent and collected informations and relevant data about them by administering PDS, EI Scale, Domestic Violence Scale, Women's Social Freedom Scale and MAQ respectively. The data were collected as per the directions of the manual concerned. Using median as cut the respondents were divided into high and low groups in respect of EI, desire for social freedom and marital adjustment. The respondents at and above median were placed in high groups and below the median were placed in low groups.

Results and Interpretations

Table - 01

Mean, SD, t-ratio showing the effect of emotional intelligence on domestic violence among the respondents.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	df	p
Emotional Intelligence	Low	92	49.32	7.32	7.68	158	<.01
	High	68	40.56	6.98			

The results displayed in the above table clearly indicated the significant effect of emotional intelligence on domestic violence of the respondents ($t = 7.68$, $df = 158$, $p < .01$). Group of respondents belonging to low emotional intelligence group were found more exposed to be the victim of domestic violence. Thus, first hypothesis of the present study is strongly supported. The finding might be interpreted on the ground that more emotionally intelligent respondents are more induced and exposed to globalization leading to have awareness towards their rights leading to be less likely the victim to domestic violence. Moreover, such women using their emotional intelligence solve their problem intelligently. But less emotionally intelligent women are unable to cope with the situation leading more likely to be the victim of domestic violence.

Table - 02

Mean, SD, t-ratio showing the influence of working status of women on domestic violence amongst women.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	df	p
Working status	Working	80	50.77	6.87	7.68	158	<.01
	Non-working	80	43.24	6.95			

Further, a significant effect of working status has been found on domestic violence of the respondents ($t = 7.68$, $df = 158$, $p < .01$). Thus, second hypothesis of the present endeavour is confirmed. The rationale of the finding is that the working women have more social freedom, individual considerations relating to the events expected to take place in the present or future life. Therefore, she must enjoy individual thinking leading to enjoy more social freedom in terms of violation of rules of the family resulting into different forms of domestic violence. On the other hand-non working women are dependent upon their husbands or other members of their family for their livelihood and even for their proper rearing of their children. Naturally, they are expected to yield before the family members and thus domestic violence are likely to be committed by them very less than their working counterparts.

Table - 03

Mean, SD, t-ratio showing the influence of desire for social freedom amongst women on their domestic violence.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	df	p
Desire for Social Freedom	High	107	52.16	7.54	6.96	158	<.01
	Low	53	44.64	5.88			

The results relating to the desire of social freedom showed a significant effect on domestic violence ($t = 6.96$; $df = 198$; $p < .01$). Thus, third hypothesis of the present study is confirmed. The finding might be interpreted on the ground that the respondents belonging to high desire for social freedom group are likely to be free from religious values, cultural values, social values and family traditions as compared to those belonging to low social freedom group. Obviously, women group of high desire for social freedom are more prone to be the victim of domestic violence than women group belonging to low desire for social freedom.

Table - 04

Mean, SD, t-value showing influence of marital adjustment on domestic violence amongst women.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	p
Marital Adjustment	Sound	78	39.08	6.75	8.54	158	<.01
	Poor	82	48.13	6.80			

Further, it is clear from the results of table-04 that there is a significant effect of marital adjustment on domestic violence of the respondents ($t = 8.54$, $df = 158$, $p < .01$). Thus, fourth hypothesis, too is confirmed. The finding is interpreted on the rationale that women having sound marital adjustment are more motivated and prompt to future oriented expectations relating to their welfare in life as well as after life. On the other hand the women belonging to poor marital adjustment group are less motivated and less privileged to avail, women expectations, and social conventions leading into more likely to become the victim of domestic violence.

Conclusions

- (i) High emotional intelligence group of women are more prone to domestic violence.
- (ii) Working women are more exposed to be the victim of domestic violence.
- (iii) Women with high desire for social freedom are more prone to domestic violence.
- (iv) Women with poor marital adjustment are more prone to domestic violence.

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